

aFungi (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*)

Metamonada

PFAM Accessions

c ATPase domain (partial) Orc1, Cdc6 and Orc1/Cdc6-like

	WA	WB	R-finger	
P54784_Saccharomyces_cerevisiae_Orc1/1-914	GTPGVGKT	VVLLDELD	S --- RIG	Orc1
Q13415_Homo_sapiens_Orc1/1-861	GVPGTGKT	VLLVDELD	S --- RLG	
Q710E8_Arabidopsis_thaliana_Orc1A/1-809	GVPGTGKT	ILLIDELD	S --- RMG	
Q9SU24_Arabidopsis_thaliana_Orc1B/1-813	GVPGTGKT	ILLIDELD	S --- RMG	
Q384U5_Trypanosomas_brucei_Orc1/1-436	GMPGTGKT	VIVVDEVD	S --- RLD	Cdc6
Q38FV5_Trypanosomas_brucei_Orc1b/1-602	GACGSGKT	VLVVDEVE	--- PHML	
P09119_Saccharomyces_cerevisiae_Cdc6/1-513	GPPGTGKT	VVVLDEMD	LD - - RGLL	
Q99741_Homo_sapiens_Cdc6/1-560	GAPGTGKT	VLVVDEMD	AR - - EKCK	
O82387_Arabidopsis_thaliana_Cdc6A/1-539	GCPGTGKS	LIIADEMD	SL - - NCK	Orc1
Q8W032_Arabidopsis_thaliana_Cdc6B/1-505	GCPGTGKS	LIIADEMD	SL - - NCK	
TVAG_340580_Trichomonas_vaginalis/1-605	GVPGTGKT	ILLIDELD	S --- RFG	
TVAG_376490_Trichomonas_vaginalis/1-593	GVPGTGKT	ILLIDELD	S --- RFG	
GL50581_2939_Giardia_intestinalis/1-372	GNPGTGKT	LLVIDEVD	S --- RLS	Orc1/Cdc6-like
GMRT_24689_Giardia_muris/1-347	GSAAAGKS	VVVIDEVD	S --- RAR	
GMRT_20170_Giardia_muris/1-347	GSAAAGKS	VVVIDEVD	S --- RAR	
g11477.t1_Kipferlia_bialata/1-443	GVPGTGKT	VLLVDELD	S --- RAG	
MONOS_13325_Monocercomonoides_exilis/1-841	GIPGTGKT	VVLIDEVD	SL - - LRG	Orc1/Cdc6-like
GL50803_17103_Giardia_intestinalis/1-372	GNPGTGKT	LIVIDEVD	S --- RLS	
GL50581_419_Giardia_intestinalis/1-354	GLPGIGKT	IYIIDEFD	AFFGANIK	
GL50803_8922_Giardia_intestinalis/1-354	GLPGIGKT	VYVIDELD	VFFGSSIK	
TPC1_15738_Trepomonas_sp/1-310	GNPASGKT	NIVIDEVD	S --- RME	Orc1/Cdc6-like
DHA2_17103_t26_1_Giardia_intestinalis/1-372	GNPGTGKT	LIVIDEVD	S --- RLS	
GLP15_1399_t26_1_Giardia_intestinalis/1-372	GNPGTGKT	LIVIDEVD	S --- RLS	
DHA2_152285_t26_1_Giardia_intestinalis/1-354	GLPGIGKT	VYVIDELD	VFFGSSIK	
GSB_17103_t26_1_Giardia_intestinalis/1-372	GNPGTGKT	LLVIDEVD	S --- RLS	Orc1/Cdc6-like
GLP15_1899_t26_1_Giardia_intestinalis/1-355	GLPGIGKT	VYVIDELD	AFFGSSIK	
SS50377_14956_Spiroucleus_salmonicida/1-280	GNPGTGKS	TLVFDEAD	SR - - AHN	
SS50377_11306_Spiroucleus_salmonicida/1-291	GNPGTGKT	VVILDEVD	QF - - LKFP	
Trichomonas_vaginalis_TVAG_467730/1-343	GNPGTGKT	IQVLDEVD	KS - - SGLS	Orc1/Cdc6-like
OHT03277.1_Tritrichomonas_foetus/1-534	GSPTGKT	LLVLDEVE	KA - - HSE	
OHT04552.1_Tritrichomonas_foetus/1-220	GDQSTGKT	LVLIDNFD	Q - - - GIS	
TPC1_13901_Trepomonas_sp/1-245	GHPGSGKT	ILVLDEID	--- LSEK	
g413.t1_Kipferlia_bialata/1-366	GQPGVGKT	LLVVDEGD	DS - - - -	

● 90-100/0.9-1.0/90-100
 ● 80-95/0.8-1.0/80-90